

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Risk Based Study of Sample Spot Fixing for Conducting Environmental Monitoring Test in Classified Areas of Pharmaceutical Industry.

Shrawan Kr. Singh*, Dr. Kamlesh Dutta, Ravi Chaudhary

Quest Pharmaceuticals, Nepal.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 03 Feb. 2025

Keywords:

Environment Monitoring Test, TAMC, TYMC, Classified Area, Finger Dab Test.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14793799

ABSTRACT

Environmental monitoring is a study Programme designed to study load of Viable Microorganism as well as Non-Viable Particles present in (controlled and classified area) environment. The use of risk assessment approaches is an important current Good Manufacturing Practice (cGMP) tool in microbiological environmental monitoring Programme. The study was designed to conduct Risk assessment study for fixing sampling point and location for conducting environmental Monitoring in Classified area. Clean rooms were divided into five groups based on different Production activities done in the plant and further the individual rooms were divided in to five different sample spot based on risk of contamination of products during activities to find the Hot spot areas for higher microbial load. Finger dab test was performed to detect the hygiene and sanitization practices in plant. In-house limit of 100 cfu was set for finger dab test as non-sterile formulation was done in plant and result was found satisfactory. The data of non-viable count was taken from third party report performed annually during rest condition. 0.5 micron and 5.0-micron particle was tested in class D area and result was satisfactory. The obtained data suggests that the worst case location is “Near Return Air Loop” in the classified areas. This location can be selected as “Hot Spot” for regular environmental monitoring of rooms..

INTRODUCTION

Environmental monitoring is a study Programme designed to study load of Viable Microorganism as well as Non-Viable Particles present in (controlled and classified area) environment. The use of risk assessment approaches is an important current Good Manufacturing Practice (cGMP)

tool in microbiological environmental monitoring Programme (1). The prime goal of environmental monitoring of cleanrooms are to regulate the numbers of airborne viable and non-viable particles within defined limits, predict the risk to the environment and regularly estimate the efficacy of cleaning and disinfecting processes

***Corresponding Author:** Shrawan Kr. Singh

Address: Quest Pharmaceuticals, Nepal.

Email ✉: Shrawan.Singh@quest.com.np

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

(2). Pharmaceutical manufacturing comprises a complicated, multi-phase processing system associated with major risks of microbial contamination through diverse sources. The product quality is greatly influenced by microbial contamination in several processing steps. There are two types of pharmaceutical products currently being manufactured are sterile and non-sterile products (3) Environment plays key role in microbial access in Pharmaceutical and biological products. The quality of product depends on environmental controls in manufacturing area. To obtain a pharmaceutical product free of contamination, you need an adequate environmental monitoring system. The system includes identification, testing and removal of bioburden to ensure the quality of product (4). The frequency of monitoring ensures contamination free environment maintenance. Environmental monitoring is a programmed scheme to explain the regulation of viable and non-viable particles in critical sites (5).

Clean Rooms

Clean Area Separation is a segregation area which is required between classified area and external environment to prevent cross contamination. According to WHO classification, it is classified as Class A, Class B, Class C and Class D and according to ISO Classification, it is classified as ISO 5, ISO 6, ISO 7 and ISO 8 (6).

Risk Assessment approach

These risk assessment approaches are not only concerned with selecting environmental monitoring locations. They integrate the environmental monitoring system with a complete review of operations within the cleanroom to ensure those facilities, operations, and practices are also satisfactory (12,13,14).

Risk Assessment Tools

A risk assessment procedure is required to determine locations for environmental monitoring. Such risk-based approaches are

recommended in ISO 14698 and regulatory authorities are increasingly asking drug manufacturers about this subject. Risk-based approaches include Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), Fault Tree Analysis (FTA), and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP), Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessment (QMRA). (10,11).

Objective of Study

1. The scope of this study, is fixing the sampling spot based on risk assessment for performing environmental monitoring.

2. To correlate the result of Finger dab test and non-viable count report with the sanitization of area and cleanliness of Personnel working in the area.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in Quest Pharmaceuticals Pvt., Ltd. The company has been manufacturing non sterile dosages forms (Tablet, Capsules, Semisolids and Soft gel capsules) and distributing its products throughout Nepal.

The research was designed on the basis of statistical sampling model as ISO 14644-1 for airborne particles quantification in cleanroom (Class D) and data was taken from third party report, Qual Tech Services, Total Aerobic Microbial Count based on risk based approach and Finger dab test to understand the cleanliness standard of personnel working in the areas. Clean rooms were divided into five groups as Dispensing Room-I, Granulation Room-I, Compression room-IV, Tablet Inspection room and Blister Packing room based on different Production activities done in the plant and further the individual rooms were divided in to five different sample spot as

- a. Near machine where production activity is done
- b. Area where the man movement is maximum
- c. Difficult to clean area
- d. Near Return Air Loop

e. Near Drainage area

based on risk of contamination of products during activities to find the Hot spot areas for higher microbial load.

Study Module for Total Aerobic Microbial Count(TAMC)

Study Period: 22/06/2022- 24/06/2022 (3 days)

Media: Soyabean Casein Digest Agar and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar

Method: Settle Plate Method (90 mm Petriplates)

Limit: Not more than 100 cfu/plate (4 hours Exposure) 25 plates of Soyabean Casein Digest Agar and 25 plates of Sabouraud Dextrose Agar was exposed for 4 hours in all sampling points.

The study was conducted for three successive days. Sterile Culture media plates were exposed on petriplates stand on respective sampling sites in each room for four hours. After completion of exposure time, the petriplates were aseptically transported to Microbiology laboratory. Soyabean Casein Digest Agar plates were incubated in incubator for 72 hours and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar petriplates were incubated in BOD Incubator for 5-7 days. After the completion of incubation period, colony on

Petriplates were counted using Colony Counter and result were interpreted.

Finger Dab Test

Finger Dab test was performed in the Dispensing Room-I, Granulation Room-I, Compression room-IV, Tablet Inspection room and Blister Packing room from the personnel working in the respective areas. In-house Limit of Finger Dab test was set to 100 cfu as the production area was operating in class D area and non-sterile solid dosages was formulated in the area. Personnel working in areas were selected randomly and each of them was evaluated by finger DAB test. All the fingers including thumb of personnel's gloves were gently imprinted and impression of all these workers were obtained on labeled Perti plates containing Soyabean casein digest agar. All the plates were incubated for at 35°C for 72 hours and results were recorded.

Non-Viable Count

Report of Third party validation is taken and is performed by Qual Tech Services as approved vendor for Clean room validation in the plant.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Result of Viable Microbial Count

1. Dispensing Room-I

S. No	Sampling Location	TAMC CFU/Plate			TYMC CFU/Plate			Result
		Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	
1	Near Machine	84	92	84	21	28	28	Complies
2	Area with maximum man movement	94	75	82	30	31	38	Complies
3	Difficult to clean area	84	81	78	24	26	32	Complies
4	Near return air loop	96	93	90	41	47	42	Complies
5	Near Drainage area	92	77	90	16	26	32	Complies

2. Granulation Room-I

S. No	Sampling Location	TAMC CFU/Plate			TYMC CFU/Plate			Result
		Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	
1	Near Machine	65	67	70	32	36	36	Complies
2	Area with maximum man movement	85	89	92	33	39	41	Complies
3	Difficult to clean area	80	76	83	25	31	32	Complies
4	Near return air loop	90	94	98	45	46	48	Complies
5	Near Drainage area	75	65	70	32	25	34	Complies

3. Compression Room-IV

S. No	Sampling Location	TAMC CFU/Plate			TYMC CFU/Plate			Result
		Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	Day-I	Day-II	Day-I	
1	Near Machine	62	71	66	25	34	36	Complies
2	Area with maximum man movement	88	78	80	28	33	36	Complies
3	Difficult to clean area	65	67	78	26	37	32	Complies
4	Near return air loop	97	86	92	46	42	44	Complies
5	Near Drainage area	80	78	84	37	40	34	Complies

4. Tablet Inspection Room

S. No	Sampling Location	TAMC CFU/Plate			TYMC CFU/Plate			Result
		Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	
1	Near Machine	17	12	22	8	10	13	Complies
2	Area with maximum	23	26	25	12	14	16	Complies

	man movement							
3	Difficult to clean area	31	33	18	17	17	23	Complies
4	Near return air loop	50	37	47	13	18	28	Complies
5	Near Drainage area	21	37	22	7	10	13	Complies

5. Blister Packing Room-II

S. No	Sampling Location	TAMC CFU/Plate			TYMC CFU/Plate			Result
		Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	Day-I	Day-II	Day-III	
1	Near Machine	90	96	87	36	37	42	Complies
2	Area with maximum man movement	96	95	88	40	42	40	Complies
3	Difficult to clean area	95	93	90	34	40	32	Complies
4	Near return air loop	99	100	97	42	45	43	Complies
5	Near Drainage area	90	88	95	38	40	40	Complies

After reviewing the results obtained for different locations of five different rooms, it can be concluded that the results are under the defined limits. The worst case location is “Near Return Air Loop”. The TAMC and TYMC, was observed

high at sampling Location “Near Return Air Loop” in comparison to the other sampling Locations for three consecutive days.

2.Result of Finger Dab Test

S.No.	Sample Code No.	Sampling Location	TAMC(CFU/Plate)	TAMC(CFU/Plate)	Result
			Right Hand	Left Hand	
1	49	Dispensing Room-I	30	42	Complies
2	99	Dispensing Room-I	67	69	Complies
3	124	Granulation Room-I.	34	28	Complies
4	91	Granulation Room-I.	40	52	Complies
5	72	Compression Room-IV	48	58	Complies
6	58	Compression Room-IV	49	48	Complies
7	42	Tablet Inspection room	66	57	Complies
8	111	Tablet Inspection room	78	65	Complies
9	56	Blister Packing Room-II	37	68	Complies
10	118	Blister Packing Room-II	67	83	Complies

In House Limit: Not more than 100 cfu/5 finger

Altogether tested 10 samples in 5 different rooms in the working areas, the cleanliness status of

personnel was found satisfactory according to In-house limit. The result of right hand (five finger)

and Left hand (five finger) was in the specified in house limit for finger dab test.

Result of Non-Viable Count (Rest Condition).

S. No.	Room /Sampling area	0.5 Micron	5.0 micron	Result
1	Dispensing Room-I	315500	6070	Complies
2	Granulation Room-I.	430496	3082	Complies
3	Compression Room-IV	303797	6700	Complies
4	Tablet Inspection room	472376	3068	Complies
5	Blister Packing Room-II	337048	2444	Complies

Limit as per ISO-14644-1:2015 in mtr³ for Particle count (7)

S. No.	ISO Class	0.5 micron	5.0 micron
1	ISO-08	35,20,000	29,300

The data from third party (Qual Tech Services) for Non-viable count under rest condition in the 5 different rooms in the working areas were satisfactory and within limit for ISO-8 class.

CONCLUSION

For determining the worst location, the obtained data of viable microbial count suggests that the worst case location is “Near Return Air Loop”. This location can be selected as “Hot Spot” for regular environmental monitoring of rooms. This study and results can be extensively used as a basis for marking the “Near Return Air Loop” of clean rooms as a “Hot Spot” use the area as regular Environment monitoring of clean rooms. As far as the result of Non-viable count and finger dab test are concerned, they are at satisfactory level for class

ISO-8.

REFERENCES

1. Good manufacturing practices for sterile pharmaceutical preparations in: WHO Expert C12ommittee on Specifications for Pharmaceutical Preparations. Forty-fourth Report, Geneva, World Health Organization, 2012.
2. ISO 11737-1. Sterilization of medical devices-Microbiological methods-
3. M. Ratajczak, D. Kubicka, P. Kamińska, Sawicka and Długaszewska., Saudi. Pharma. J. 2015, 23(3), 303-307.
4. V. Parag, K. Vivekanand Bhatia., J. Pharma. Res. Clinic. Practice. 2014, 4(3), 22-32.
5. USP. Microbiological control and monitoring environments used for the manufacture of healthcare products, Chapter 1116, Pharm Forum., 2007, 33(3).
6. USP NF (1116) Microbiological Control and Monitoring of Aseptic Processing Environments.
7. ISO 14644-1. Cleanrooms and associated controlled environments, classification of air cleanliness, 2015.
8. ISO 14644-2 Cleanrooms and Associated Controlled Environments – Specifications for Testing and Monitoring to prove continued compliance with ISO 14644-1.
9. ISO 14698-1 Cleanrooms and Associated Controlled Environments Bio contamination Control – Part 1: General Principles.
10. W. Whyte. and T. Eaton. ‘Microbiological Contamination Models for Use in Risk Assessment during Pharmaceutical Production,’ European Journal of Parenteral and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2004 Vol. 9, No.1, pp: 11-15.
11. W. Whyte. and T. Eaton. ‘Microbiological Risk Assessment in Pharmaceutical Cleanrooms,’ European Journal of Parenteral

- and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2004, Vol. 9, No.1, pp: 16-23.
12. T. Sandle. 'The Use of a Risk Assessment in the Pharmaceutical Industry – the Application of FMEA to a Sterility Testing Isolator: a Case Study,' *European Journal of Parenteral and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2003 8(2): 43-49.
 13. T. Sandle 'Selection and Use of Cleaning and Disinfection Agents in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing' in Hodges, N and Hanlon, G. (2003): 'Industrial Pharmaceutical Microbiology Standards and Controls,' Euromed Communications, England.
 14. T. Sandle. 'General Considerations for the Risk Assessment of Isolators Used for Aseptic Processes,' *Pharmaceutical Manufacturing and Packaging Sourcer*, Samedan Ltd, Winter 2004, pp: 43-47.
 15. PDA Technical Report No. 13 (revised): 'Fundamentals of an Environmental Monitoring Programme,' September/October 2001..

HOW TO CITE: Shrawan Kr. Singh*, Dr. Kamlesh Dutta, Ravi Chaudhary, Risk Based Study of Sample Spot Fixing for Conducting Environmental Monitoring Test in Classified Areas of Pharmaceutical Industry, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 2, 146-152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14793799>

